

Scurvy described by M. Dellon (1681)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

This is James Lind's English summary of a text on scurvy by Dellon in 1681.

1681. **Dellon**, a French physician.

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Yellow is used to indicate the description of symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

The text below is from Lind (1772; 3rd ed) p.378-380.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/378/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/378/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uclm.5320216006&seq=402>

<https://hdl.handle.net/2027/uclm.5320216006>

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1683

Une voyage aux Indes orientales, escrit par M. Dellon, M. D. supplement, chap. 2.
Of the scurvy, called by the *French* the land evil.

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This is the most dangerous and troublesome of all the distempers incident in a long voyage, being contagious, and scarce ever to be cured at sea. The symptoms first appear in the mouth and gums, which swell, grow black, and emit a disagreeable scent. Deep incisions are requisite in order to remove a considerable quantity of corrupted flesh and matter, which not only loosens the teeth, but makes them fall out. The next symptoms that appear are certain black spots on the arms, legs, and thighs, and then over the body. The broader these spots are, and the nearer the heart, the more dangerous is the distemper. The corruption in the gums, and

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blotches over the body, are followed by a *nausea*, laziness, fainting fits, pains in the head, arms, and legs, and last of all with a looseness. There is seldom any fever; the pulse in this malady declining very little from its natural state.

For prevention he recommends that the ship be victualled with sound wholesome provisions; that she be kept neat and clean, washed with sea-water every day, and sprinkled with vinegar twice or thrice a week. Each person on board ought to provide himself with juice of *citrons, lemons,*

*ros solis*¹, and dried fruits, especially prunes, and not to abstain long from drinking. But if the disease has already made its attack, then he proposes first a moderate bleeding, a little gentle physic, and above all repeated clysters², if there is not a scarcity of water on board. The gums are to be rubbed with a mixture of vinegar or juice of lemons with some salt, until they bleed. The blotches on the body are to be washed and rubbed with warm sea-water until they smart: or (if it can be got) with the blood of a sea hog, which has been found by experience to have a specific quality against this evil. If in spite of all endeavours the heart becomes affected with the malignant vapours from the corrupted parts, recourse must be had to cordials. From the first attack of the disease, the patient must abstain

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from every thing salted. If he cannot have fresh provisions, he must feed on rice, barley, and prunes, and drink wine mixed with water, which will be of greater service to him than all the cordials in the ship. He concludes with telling us, that it is of great use to send the sick on shore in hot weather or in warm countries; but if the ship comes to an anchor in a cold climate, the utmost care is to be taken not to expose them to a cold air. They are rather to be kept up close and warm, sweating being conducive to their cure, especially if at the same time they are provided with a good diet of easy digestion, and good nourishment.

1 Ros solis. A cordial flavored with juice from the sundew or other herbs and spices.

2 Clyster. The rectal administration of a fluid by injection into the lower bowel via the anus.